

Tutorial: How to Use the CircleCI Grammar

The CircleCI grammar allows you to define CI/CD pipelines with various elements like jobs, environments, triggers, containers, inputs, outputs, and more.

CircleCI DSL supports content assist feature that helps users write their pipeline faster.

How to Use:

1. Activate Content Assist:
 - While writing your CICD pipeline, press `CTRL+SPACE` to bring up the content assist menu.
2. Navigate Suggestions:
 - Use the arrow keys to navigate through the list of suggestions.
3. Select a Suggestion:
 - Press `ENTER` or double-click to select a suggestion and insert it into your document.

Start by writing Pipeline keyword. Then give an Enter and Tab to write version "2.1". This is because version is a Pipeline attribute and so we need to preserve the hierarchy.

Then press Enter and Backspace to finish the Pipeline block and press Enter to create a Docker named "default" with image "circleci/node:10" and medium resourceClass.

```
-----  
Pipeline  
  version "2.1"
```

```
Docker  
  name "default"  
  image "circleci/node:10"  
  resourceClass medium  
-----
```

It's becoming apparent that keywords with capital letters are objects and lower-case keywords their attributes. To define an attribute or another object of a parent object, press Enter and TAB.

Now create a Job named "build" by writing Job and press Enter and TAB to specify the Job name. This Job reuses "default" executor (Docker "default" executor), has a RestoreCache with keys 'v1-{{ checksum "yarn.lock" }}' (press Enter and Tab to define keys), then press Enter and Backspace to close RestoreCache block.

```
-----  
Pipeline  
  version "2.1"  
  
Docker  
  name "default"  
  image "circleci/node:10"  
  resourceClass medium  
  
Job  
  name "build"  
  reuseExecutor "default"  
  RestoreCache  
    keys 'v1-{{ checksum "yarn.lock" }}'  
-----
```

This Job also has a SaveCache with paths "node_modules" and key 'v1-{{ checksum "yarn.lock" }}', and a Run with a RunCommand named "yarn install --frozen-lockfile".

```
-----  
Pipeline  
  version "2.1"  
  
Docker  
  name "default"  
  image "circleci/node:10"  
  resourceClass medium  
  
Job  
  name "build"  
  reuseExecutor "default"  
  RestoreCache  
    keys 'v1-{{ checksum "yarn.lock" }}'  
  SaveCache  
    paths "node_modules"  
    key "v1-{{ checksum 'yarn.lock' }}"  
  Run  
    RunCommand  
      name "yarn install --frozen-lockfile"
```

To finish, close Job block (Enter and Backspaces) to create a Workflow named "build-and-deploy", with version "2.1" and it has a JobWorkflow named "build"

This is the result:

```
-----  
Pipeline  
  version "2.1"  
  
Docker  
  name "default"  
  image "circleci/node:10"  
  resourceClass medium  
  
Job  
  name "build"  
  reuseExecutor "default"  
  RestoreCache  
    keys 'v1-{{ checksum "yarn.lock" }}'  
  SaveCache  
    paths "node_modules"  
    key "v1-{{ checksum 'yarn.lock' }}"  
  Run  
    RunCommand  
      name "yarn install --frozen-lockfile"  
  
Workflow  
  name "build-and-deploy"  
  version "2.1"  
  
  JobWorkflow  
    name "build"
```

You now finished the tutorial!